

STILL SUFFERING: A SURVEY BASED ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN

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Once the first Prime Minister of India, Jawaharlal Nehru said, "you can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women". But we don't know if it is true or not still in today's life, because in whole world we can see the opposite site of those words. In India women face violence at every stage in their life cycle. Violence against women is enacted in the practices of female foeticide, female infanticide, girl child neglect, physical and sexual abuse, child marriage, eve testing, and sexual harassment in the work place, domestic violence and even dowry death. Violence against women has been clearly defined as a form of discrimination in numerous documents. The World Human Right Conference in Vienna, first recognized gender-based violence as a human right violation in 1993. In the same year United Nations Declaration, 1993, defined violence against women as "any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivations of liberty whether occurring in public or private life". The paper shows and discusses the survey based present scenario of women in Kalna sub-division and nearby villages in Burdwan district about the different type of daily sufferings what they are facing regularly in the road, houses and in many other ways. All types of violence are divided accordingly like domestic violence, eve teasing, child marriage, sexual harassment, dowry, negligence in women health, extortion for being girl child etc. and being discussed by age wise, area wise and employment wise respectively. The paper also highlights the legal reform procedures of women in the present context of west Bengal.

Key words: Violence, Sufferings

Introduction:

In India women face violence at every stage in their life cycle. Violence against women is enacted in the practices of female foeticide, female infanticide, girl child neglect, physical and sexual abuse, child marriage, eve testing, and sexual harassment in the work place, domestic violence and even dowry death. Although many of these practices are found in all countries, many expression of violence against women are particular to the Indian socio cultural context. The institution of dowry, despite its illegality, is an ever present specter, and whilst it remains; the problem of son preference and the embedded ideas of gender inequality will pervade.

In the last two decades violence against women has emerged as the most burning and intractable social problem across regional, social, and cultural boundaries. Violence against women is recognized as a serious human right violation and pervasive public health problem that concern all sector of society. Irrespective of a nation's level of development, women are susceptible to exploitation, oppression and other types of demeaning violence from men in all societies where cultural norms, tradition and the legal system endorse women's subordination to men. In the south Asian region, violence against women begins long before they are born and continues throughout their lives. The lives of unborn girl are terminated through sex selective abortion. Every sixth death of a female infant in India, Bangladesh and Pakistan is due to neglect and discrimination. In the region females face restrictions in mobility, usually have less to eat than their male counterpart, are denied proper education and health care, are often forced into early marriage, have few opportunities of employment and are underrepresented in the government. Violence against women has been clearly defined as a form of discrimination in numerous documents. The world human right conference in Vienna first recognized gender-based violence as a human right violation in 1993. In the same year United Nations declaration, 1993 defined violence against women as "any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivations of liberty whether occurring in public or private life".

Historical Perspective:

The acceptance of gender equality in the constitution of independent India provided women with a basis for a new identity, as full citizens of the republic and a source of their right to equality, dignity and justice in other spheres of life. But long before such constitutional guarantee came through, the struggle for legal reforms has always been central to organized efforts in improving women's status in India. In the social reformers of the nineteenth century, women in independence movement and women in the contemporary women's movement turned to law as a vehicle for improving women's social, economic, political, and cultural status.

Nineteenth century reformers like Raja Rammohun Roy campaigned for abolition of sati, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar fought for widow remarriage and the issue of child marriage was taken up in the later half of the century by Behram Malabari and Ranade. In the later part of the century women came to the forefront and campaigned mainly for their education and public participation. Women's organizations at the all-India level began emerging in the early part of the twentieth century and their agenda include advocacy of women's suffrage, the issue of child marriage and campaign for reforming the personal laws.

The Hindu personal law underwent a major reform with the passing of Child Marriage Restraint Act in 1928. Since the early thirties women's organizations like AIWC and Women's Indian Association began pressing for Hindu Code. It would remove all legal disabilities of women in marriage and inheritance. The Hindu Code Bill was finally passed as late as 1955. While Indian women achieved formal political and economic equality, their role in the private sphere was left fundamentally unchallenged until the autonomous woman's movement of the late seventies and eighties. The nineties witnessed the historic passing of the 73rd and 74th Amendments to the constitution (1993) conferring constitutional status on local self government bodies as integral parts of Indian's democratic governance structure and mandating one-third reservation for women in all these bodies, with-in-built quotas for schedule caste and tribe women. These two along with the pending 81st Amendment Bill (1996) seeking to reserve one-third seats for women, are bound to have long term implication on the future of India's democracy and governance.

Defining Violence Against Women:

Despite the existence of a World Wide Movement against Violence against Women, there is no single accepted definition of violence. The main point of contention is how broadly to define the term. Some argue for a very broad definition that includes any Act or omission that causes harm to women to keep them in a subordinate position. For example, the definition in the draft Pan American Treaty against violence defines, violence against women as any Act omission or conduct by means of which physical, sexual or mental suffering is inflicted, directly or indirectly through deceit, seduction threat coercion or any other means, or any women with the purpose or effect of intimidating punishing or humiliating her or of maintaining her in sex-stereotype roles or of denying her human dignity sexual self determination, physical, mental and moral integrity or of under mining the security of her person, her self-respect or her personality or of diminishing her physical or mental capacities. Under such a definition any structural feature that perpetuates gender-based discrimination could arguably qualify as violence. Violence against women is a manifestation of historically unequal power relations between men and women which have led to domination over and discrimination against, women by men. Violence against women is one of the crucial social mechanism by which women are forced in to a subordinate position.

Types of Violence Against Women:

Phase	Type of Violence
Pre-birth	Sex-selective abortion; effects of battering during pregnancy on birth outcomes.
Infancy	Female infanticide; physical, sexual and Psychological abuse.
Girlhood	Child marriage; female genital mutilation; physical Sexual, psychological abuse; incest; child Prostitution and pornography.
Adolescence And Adulthood	Dating and courtship violence (e.g., acid throwing); economically coerced sex; incest; sexual abuse in the Work place; rape; sexual harassment; forced Prostitution and pornography; trafficking in women; Partner violence; marital rape; dowry abuse & Murders; partner homicide; psychological abuse; Abuse of women with disabilities; forced pregnancy.
Elderly	Forced suicide or homicide of widows for economic Reasons; sexual physical and psychological abuse

The Survey:

A detailed survey was conducted by the author in the Kalna sub-division and nearby villages on eve teasing, child marriage, sexual harassment, domestic violence, dowry, misbehaving for having girl child and negligence of women health in the months of January and February of 2015. Though it was not purely research based activities but still the results were very annoying itself for all of us and should be known to the common mass. It is stated below with brief notes on those types of violence.

Eye Teasing:

The term Eye teasing is used to refer to sexual harassment of women in public places such as the streets, public transportation, parks, beaches, and cinema halls. This type of a public harassment by a lone man or gangs of women includes such as verbal assaults such as making passes or unwelcome sexual jokes: nonverbal assaults such as showing obscene gestures, winking, whistling, and staring, and physical assaults such as pinching, fondling and rubbing against women in public places. In addition, several instances of eye teasing have been followed by more violent assaults such as rape and murder. Many psychologists believe that sex, love or fun is not the only motive that men indulge in this behavior. Eye teasing is closely related to the patriarchal mindset of the Indian male. Men are raised to believe that they are more powerful physically and emotionally than women. They feel that they are doing nothing wrong just having some fun. Women on the other hand are made to feel vulnerable and the weaker sex. Teachers of psychology and social scientists believe eye teasing to be a result of the frustrations suffered by a majority of youth. Disappointed by the unbecoming attitude of teachers and indifferent parents, they yearn for an outlet to vent their aggression and depression. Besides, many who do not inherit good values tend to indulge in acts of sexual harassment. Eye teasing can be seen as a rite of passage for boys on their way to becoming men. Considering that sex is not the only motive, it would be reasonable to conclude that the psychodynamics of eye teasing are closely linked to the issue of masculinity and the masculine agenda. At the risk of over simplifying a complex phenomenon, it would not be imprudent to say that in our country, the construct of masculinity is usually equated with patriarchy.

Survey Report on Eye Teasing

Age Wise

Age Limit	No. of Women Surveyed	Victim of Eye Teasing	Not Victim of Eye Teasing	Percentage of Victim of Eye Teasing
Below 30	36	28	08	77
30 to 50	53	18	35	34
Above 50	11	03	08	27

Area Wise

Area	No. of Women Surveyed	Victim of Eye Teasing	Not Victim of Eye Teasing	Percentage of Victim of Eye Teasing
Urban	50	31	19	62
Rural	50	18	32	36

It was found 58% of women whose age is below 30 are facing eye teasing in their life. After that whose age is between 30 to 50, nearly 34% of them are facing this problem. Above 50 aged women are also facing this eye teasing. It is for them about 27%. It is because, according to the researcher, most of the eye teasers are from young ages. For that reason they do this to their young ages. And obviously it is a reason that the attractiveness and beauty with their dress always lie between these time. When eye teasing is compared between urban areas and rural areas then it was seen it is more (48%) in the urban areas than rural areas (36%). It is because mainly, what was observed; there exist many clubs, rocks and other entertainments mainly in the urban areas. Adding to this colleges and universities are also located in the urban areas. And all we know that these are the perfect places for them to do eye teasing.

Child Marriage:

It was a norm in medieval India. Girls were married off at the age of 8-10. They were not allowed access to education and were treated as the material being. The plight of women can be imagined by one of the shloka of Tulsidas where he writes [r1] "Dhol, gawar, shudra, pashu, nari, ye sab tadan ke adhikari". Meaning that animals, illiterates, lower castes and women should be subjected to beating. Thus women were compared with animals and were married off at an early age. The child marriage along with it brought some more problems such as increased birth rate, poor health of women due to repeated child bearing and high mortality rate of women and children. Child marriage has been illegal in India. Since the passing of Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929. In this act, the term child refers to a male younger than twenty-one, or a female younger than eighteen. A marriage falls under the scope of this Act if either of the contracting parties meets its definition of child. Every year children are still married illegally in India. Most of the child marriages in India take place in rural villages and areas that usually have little legal supervision. Over times child marriage has become a social taboo with the majority of Indians believing it to be wrong.

However, mass marriages that involve children are frequently ignored by authorities. Child marriage, we can explain it as a social violence against women. Because at the time of marriage she has no idea about marriage. But for her family pressure she gives her view to marry. We can see every year lots of girl child marriage held in our area because now a days girl child is a burden in many families.

Survey Report on Child Marriage

Area Wise

Area	No. of Women Surveyed	Married Before Prescribed Date	Married After Prescribed Date	Percentage of Child Marriage
Urban	50	8	42	16
Rural	50	29	21	58

From this report it is seen that Child marriage is still prevailing in the rural areas. It is very much alarming because more than half of the child (58%) is given marriage in those rural areas. Moreover it is very interesting to see that in the urban areas also marriage is happening before the minimum age is attained. Though the percentage is not like rural areas but knowing all about it, it is very much shameful to us.

Sexual Harassment:

Sexual harassment is any unwanted sexual attention a woman experiences. It includes leering, pinching, patting, repeated comments, subtle suggestions of a sexual nature, and pressure for dates. Sexual harassment can occur in any situation where men have power over women: welfare workers with clients, doctors with patients, police officers with women members of a police force, or teachers with students. In the workplace, the harasser may be an employer, a supervisor, a co-worker, a client, or a customer. Sexual harassment can escalate; women who are being sexually harassed are at risk of being physically abused or raped. Sexual harassment is a powerful way for men to undermine and control women.. There is an implicit (and sometimes explicit) message that women's refusal to comply with the harasser's demands will lead to work-related reprisals. These can include escalation of harassment; poor work assignments; sabotaging of projects; denial of raises, benefits, or promotion; and sometimes the loss of the job with only a poor reference to show for it. Harassment can drive women out of a particular job or out of the workplace altogether. Socializing at work too often includes flirting or joking about sex. Although it may be a pleasant relief from routine or a way to communicate with someone we are interested in, this banter can become insulting or demeaning. It becomes sexual harassment when it creates a hostile, intimidating, or pressured working environment. There is such a taboo in many workplaces and schools against identifying sexual harassment for what it is that many of women who experience it are at first aware only of feeling stressed. Women may experience headaches, anxieties, or resistance to going to work in the morning. It may take women a while to realize that these symptoms come from women being sexually harassed. Women often respond by feeling isolated and powerless, afraid to say no or to speak out because women fear either those women somehow are responsible or that women won't receive help in facing possible retaliation

Survey Report on Sexual Harassment

Area Wise

Area	No. of Women Surveyed	Sexual Harassed	Sexual Not Harassed	Percentage of Harassment
Urban	28	04	24	14
Rural	12	01	11	8

In this part the present researcher surveyed only 40 women in these areas. It is because many of them do not want to tell anything about this subject. The researcher went at least to 100 women to ask whether they have faced any sexual harassment in home or in outside, but they were not eager to tell anything about this. They were wanting to avoid this subject. This is what is happening in the real life also. From that we can surely understand how they will respond to the common mass after being sexually harassed. So though the researcher surveyed only 40 women, there will be a doubt about their truth ness of telling. Only 14% and 8% women admitted that they were the victims of sexual harassment in urban and rural areas respectively.

Domestic Violence:

Domestic violence can be described as when one adult in a relationship misuses power to control another. It is the establishment of control and fear in the relationship through violence and other forms of abuse. It is basically

an abuse of power. The abuser tortures and controls the victim by calculated threats, intimidation and physical violence. Although men, women and children can all be abused, in most cases the victims are women. These physical attacks may also include rape and sexual violence. Psychological violence includes verbal abuse, harassment, confinement and deprivation of physical, financial and personal resources. For some women emotional abuse may be more painful than the physical attacks because they effectively undermine women's security and self-confidence. Violence within the home is universal across culture, religion, class and ethnicity. The abuse is generally condoned by social custom and considered part and parcel of marital life. Domestic violence is not only about physical injury to a spouse or partner. The physical aspect is just one type of violent behavior that an individual encounters. The primary aim of an abuser is to dominate his victim. He will seek to accomplish this in whatever way possible. Therefore, domestic violence can also be emotional, sexual, financial, etc. in nature. Domestic abuse can affect people of any caste, religion, and financial background. Physical abuse also involves behavior like grabbing, kicking, choking, pinching, and throwing things. An attacker may also be inclined to use weapons to assault his spouse. It is common for an abuser to cause irreparable damage or kill his victims in a fit of rage if the violence in the relationship is allowed to go unchecked.

Emotional or psychological abuse is another way for an abuser to gain control over his victim. The abuser may indulge in verbal abuse such as name calling, shouting, shaming, and blaming the victim for something she did not do. The non-verbal aspect involves isolation, humiliation, intimidation, etc. The abuser aims to make his partner lose her independence and self-esteem. This makes the victim unable to leave the relationship because she feels she cannot live without her abuser. Emotional abuse is dangerous because it can go undetected for a long time. Since most of the abusive behavior happens at home, detection depends on the victim coming forward or confiding in someone. In addition, victims of this type of abuse often do not even realize that abuse is taking place.

Sexual abuse refers to a situation in which one partner is forced to take part in unwanted, unsafe, or degrading sexual activity. Sexual abuse is considered the hidden form of abuse since victims rarely speak up. This type of abuse is common in relationships where a partner is also being physically abused. According to the National Coalition against Domestic Violence in America, nearly half of physically abused victims reported being raped at least once during the relationship. Financial abuse may also be a part of the abusive behavior pattern. In this type of abuse, the abuser retains control of the entire financial situation in the household. The abuser will often give the victim a small amount of money as an allowance and make her account for the entire amount. At times, he may refuse to give his partner any money at all. This could eventually lead to a stage where the abuser denies his victim necessities like food, clothing, shelter, and medical aid. Financial abuse also encompasses those cases where a partner is prevented from working or the abuser constantly tries to sabotage her career. Abusers may even steal money from their victim's accounts or use assets of the victim without her consent. All the money obtained is used solely by the abuser.

Dowry:

Dowry (a.k.a. *dahej* and *varadakshine*) is a form of wedding gift prevalent in India, which is also sometimes called *price-of-the-groom*. The dowry system was a security blanket for married women in case of marital problems or abandonment by husband. It was an *emergency fund* setup by the bride's father and brothers and was rarely cash, and instead consisted of valuables such as jewelry, and immovable property. The dowry system also acted as the girl's inheritance from her father, because the Hindu joint-family system afforded all the property to the male descendants. Over a period of time, the abuse of the dowry practice has developed in India to the extent that it has become the biggest problem facing women. Many marriages are strained because of the dispute over dowry, and during 1980s, numerous cases of "burning brides" were reported in the media, where newly wed girls either committed suicide or burnt alive by the in-laws over dowry disputes.

As girls started expecting a fair inheritance from their fathers, the grooms also started demanding more and more. Some people went to the extent of deciding such matters as love, status, and prestige in the society depending on how much dowry a family could bring (or afford), and those who could not afford an expected dowry were subjected to humiliation. As the women in India got more educated, many of them thought that the system of dowry was demeaning to women. The Indian courts have banned the practice since 1961, forgetting that it is indeed a strongly rooted tradition. So in today's India, the dowry system plays a huge, but largely underground and illegal role in match-making, and forming of marriage alliances. It is the dowry system that is the primary cause of female infanticide in India, and the primary reason why everybody wants to have only male children. The system of *gift-giving* has turned into a system of *absurd demands*, and one of harassment of women.

Survey Report on Dowry

Area Wise

Area	No. of Women Surveyed	Dowry Given	Dowry Not Given	Percentage of Giving
Urban	50	36	14	72
Rural	50	44	06	88

From this survey report it can be analyzed that whatever it is in rural or in urban areas the dowry giving is still pertaining in the population. Though there exist some strict laws against it but it is not much implemented on the minds of people and to the society. Here in the rural areas 88% of women were still giving dowry and in the urban areas only slight decrease in the percentage of dowry giving was noticed which is 72%.

Age Wise

Age Limit	No. of Women Surveyed	Dowry Given	Dowry Not Given	Percentage of Giving
Below 40	36	26	10	72
40 to 60	53	51	02	96
Above 60	11	03	08	27

When it was analyzed age wise it was found that 96% of women whose age is between 40 to 60 has given dowry. With that it is very alarming that the so called new generation i.e. aged below 40 are still giving dowry (75) in spite of knowing all the laws and others. It is low (27%) for the aged women (above 60), because at that time, very interestingly, dowry existed but inversely as told by them.

Employed / Unemployed Wise

Employed or Unemployed	No. of Women Surveyed	Dowry Given	Dowry Not Given	Percentage of Giving
Employed	18	03	15	16
Unemployed	82	77	05	94

Here it was surveyed to the employee women and house wives or unemployed women and it was noticed that though they are employee but also 33% of women were giving dowry at the time of their marriage. And a alarming high of 94% of women had given dowry, those who are actually typical house wives.

Misbehave For Having Girlchild:

As women were supposed to be and in some areas of India are still considered to be curse by some strata of society their birth was taken as a burden. So in past times they were killed as soon as they were born. In some of the Rajput clans of Rajasthan newly born girl child was dropped in a large bowl of milk and was killed. Today with the help of technology the sex of the unborn baby is determined and if it is a girl child then it is aborted down. In all this procedure women do not have any say they have to do according to the wish of their husbands even if she does not want to abort not even related to their own life. They have to take permission of male members for each and every issue. They don't have any say in important household matters and not in matter of their own life. For this reason by pressure of family laws and the husband of the women are given pressure for male child. Even women have to bear beating, slapping and is also one type of domestic violence. Every day we can watch this type of news through media.

Survey Report for Having Girl child

Area Wise

Area	No. of Women Surveyed	Faced Problem	Not Faced Problem	Percentage of Facing Problem
Urban	25	10	15	40
Rural	25	16	09	64

In this survey it was asked to them some questions like - After having girl child at the time of her birth what was the reaction of her husband, father-in-law or mother-in-law or now is she facing any problem for that or still she has to hear many words for giving birth a girl child etc. After this it is observed that they were still facing and hearing many insulting words for being girl child. In the rural area 64% of women still facing this type of problem, and very surprisingly in the urban area also around 40% of women facing similar type of problem

Conclusio:

Once the first Prime Minister of India, Jawaharlal Nehru said, "You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women". We don't know if it is true or not. Because in whole world we can see the opposite site of those word. We don't know what the conclusion of this is. My effort was to know the status of women's' sufferings in many forms still in this 2015 era of time. It is really very ridiculous and at the same time very irritating and annoying that our mothers, sisters and many other types of relationship are in this position. It is clear that violence against women is endemic in our area and perhaps also in our India. The reason is women in the country are highly vulnerable because of poor quality of life indicate by rampant poverty, lack of education, poor health status, high fertility rate & high maternal mortality rate. Added with that contributing to the violence against women in social mindset about women that has not changed much. Violence is perpetrated on women both inside and outside her home.

This is a good site that the government and voluntary organization are making efforts towards ending or minimizing violence against women. The efforts of the government are in the shape of enacting relevant legislations, issuing orders and launching various women welfare scheme. But their implementation remains tardy, as the lower level government functionaries are not gender sensitive. On the other hand the voluntary organizations are taking both preventive as well as reactionary measures. But efforts of the voluntary organizations suffer from paucity of funds and in fracture. Yet in this rather bleak scenario; many voluntary organizations have devised several innovative strategies to combat the menace and been successful in wiping tears of helpless women.

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